

International Journal of Basic, Applied and Innovative Research

IJBAIR, 2025, 13(1): 20-30

ISSN: 2315 - 5388

www.arpijournals.com; www.antrescentpub.com.

E-ISSN: 2384 - 681X

RESEARCH PAPER

BODY MASS INDEX, HAND LENGTH AND FOOT LENGTH MORPHOMETRY OF THE OKRIKA PEOPLE IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

¹Okoseimiema, S.C., ²Kalio, E., ¹Ebhojaye, I.K., ¹Sunday, I.P., ³Christian, U., ⁴Obomanu-Tamunotonjo, R. & ¹Collins, G.U.

¹Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Port Harcourt; ²Department of Biomedical Technology, School of Science Laboratory Technology, University of Port Harcourt; ³Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, River State University; ⁴Department of Medical Biochemistry, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Port Harcourt.

Correspondence Email: ruth.omimi-inabuaye@uniport.edu.ng

Received: 3rd February, 2025

Accepted: 17th March, 2025

Published: 31st March, 2025

Endorsed By: Innovative Science Research Foundation (ISREF) and International Society of Science Researchers (ISSCIR).

Indexed By: African Journal Online (AJOL) and IRMS Informatics India (J-Gate)

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to determine the Body Mass Index (BMI) of the Okrika ethnic group of Rivers State, Nigeria, while also assessing potential sexual dimorphism and ethnic variations in BMI, foot length, and hand length. A total of 375 subjects participated in the study. The mean weight of males (71.36 ± 12.24 kg) was significantly higher than that of females (65.52 ± 13.96 kg) ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, hand length was greater in males (18.83 ± 2.04 cm) than in females (17.48 ± 2.03 cm) ($p < 0.05$). Foot length followed the same trend, with males measuring 25.26 ± 2.70 cm and females 23.88 ± 2.34 cm ($p < 0.05$). However, BMI values for males (23.11 ± 4.53) and females (23.34 ± 5.24) showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$). The mean height was significantly higher in males (176.38 ± 12.46 cm) than in females (168.03 ± 12.25 cm) ($p < 0.05$). These findings provide baseline anthropometric data specific to the Okrika ethnic group of Rivers State, Nigeria, which will be valuable to biomedical technologists, clinicians, and forensic anthropologists. The study also emphasizes the importance of population-specific data in clinical assessments and suggests further research on BMI variations among other Nigerian ethnic groups.

Key words: Anthropometry, Body Mass Index, Foot length, Hand length, Okrika,, Stature estimation

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is a condition characterized by excessive body fat accumulation (Bosy-Westphal, 2021)). Due to the difficulty in directly measuring body fat, obesity is commonly assessed using the Body Mass Index (BMI), calculated as weight in kilograms divided by the square of height in meters (Mohajan, 2023). BMI is widely used to categorize individuals as underweight (BMI < 18.5), normal weight (18.5–24.9), overweight (25.0–29.9), or obese (≥ 30.0). This classification allows for comparisons across different races, age groups, and sexes. The prevalence of obesity varies significantly among populations and is influenced by multiple factors such as genetics, diet, and lifestyle. Research indicates that obesity rates tend to increase steadily between the ages of 20 and 60 before declining (Huayi *et al.*, 2023) Food intake plays a crucial role in determining BMI, with macronutrients such as fat, carbohydrates, and protein serving as primary energy sources (Grech *et al.*, 2022). Weight gain occurs when caloric intake exceeds energy expenditure, while weight

loss happens when energy expenditure surpasses intake. Dehydration can slow down fat metabolism, emphasizing the importance of adequate hydration in maintaining a healthy BMI.

Environmental factors also play a significant role in determining BMI. Individuals in stable environments with access to adequate food and minimal stress are more likely to gain weight than those in less favorable conditions, such as war zones, where food scarcity and stress levels are high (Fawehinmi and Oladipo, 2004). Moreover, genetics contributes to variations in BMI, with research suggesting that obesity tends to run in families. The likelihood of developing obesity is significantly higher among first-degree relatives of obese individuals, emphasizing the role of hereditary factors (Bouchard, 2021). Beyond genetic and environmental influences, obesity is linked to numerous health complications, including diabetes, hypertension, heart disease, infertility, and increased mortality. Conversely, individuals with a low BMI are at a heightened risk of developing conditions such as osteoporosis, ulcers, and severe malnutrition-related illnesses.

Obesity and BMI variations arise from several interrelated factors, including dietary habits, genetic predisposition, environmental influences, and socioeconomic status. Studies indicate that maintaining energy balance—where energy intake matches expenditure—is crucial for a stable BMI (Hall *et al.*, 2022). Research by Škop *et al.*, (2023) highlights the role of physical activity in energy expenditure, with reduced activity levels contributing to weight gain. Additionally, socioeconomic status significantly affects obesity rates. Reyes *et al.*, (2020) relates that obesity prevalence was higher among women in lower socioeconomic classes, with 30% of low-income women classified as obese compared to just 5% in high-income groups. Cultural perceptions further shape weight-related attitudes, as studies have shown that black women tend to view themselves as attractive despite being overweight, whereas white women express greater dissatisfaction with their weight (Sahasorn *et al.*, 2002; Watson and Moody, 2019).

Anthropometric measurements, including hand and foot length, have been extensively used to estimate stature across different populations. Studies by MacDonel (1901) and Davenport and Steggerda (1929) have revealed population-specific variations in foot length-to-stature ratios. More recent research (Mohanty *et al.*, 2001; Mansur *et al.*, 2012) has further developed regression equations for height estimation based on foot length, confirming the reliability of these measurements in forensic anthropology. The accuracy of these estimations is crucial for various applications, including forensic investigations, archaeological reconstructions, and medical diagnostics.

This research aims to characterize the BMI patterns of the Okrika ethnic group, contributing to the broader understanding of health and nutrition within this population. By determining the average BMI, assessing foot and hand length, examining sexual dimorphism, and comparing results with other ethnic groups, this study will provide valuable insights into forensic anthropology and public health. Previous research has emphasized the importance of anthropometric measurements in stature estimation and health assessments (Robbins, 1978; Stewart, 1979; Rogers, 1987). The findings from this study will not only facilitate BMI education among the Okrika people but also enhance knowledge about obesity trends and health risks associated with BMI variations. (Sarma *et al.*, 2021).

This study also seeks to bridge the gap in literature regarding BMI trends among the Okrika ethnic group. By examining BMI in conjunction with hand and foot length measurements, the research aims to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of body composition among this population. The findings will serve not only as a valuable resource for BMI education among the Okrika people but also as comparative data for analyzing racial and ethnic differences in anthropometric trends. Additionally, the study's conclusions may provide insights into public health interventions aimed at addressing obesity and malnutrition within the region.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study area: This research was carried out on the people of Okrika people of Rivers State. Okrika, is a port town in Rivers State, Nigeria, has a distinct demographic and economic profile. The establishment of the Okrika federation,

Kirike Se, was the outcome of multiple migrations from different areas and evolution into a community of people speaking one language and living one culture. However, there is a dominant tendency to assume that the first settlers Okrika came from the Ijo settlements of the Central Niger Delta (Obuoforibo, 2012). However, evidence also suggest that non-Central Niger Delta migrants established many Okrika settlements and contributed to the institutionalization of its traditions, customs and culture. (Asuk and Adubo, 2020).

The town is located on Okrika Island along the Bonny River and has historically played an important role in trade and commerce. While it initially thrived in the 17th century as a center for the slave trade, it later became a hub for palm oil exportation after the abolition of slavery. By 1965, the establishment of the Port Harcourt refinery and the construction of pipelines revived Okrika as a commercial port. Presently, refined petroleum products constitute a major part of its exports. According to the 2006 census, the Okrika Local Government Area had a population of 222,026, with an estimated 145,000 Okrika natives residing abroad, primarily in the United Kingdom and the United States. Despite the economic and historical significance of Okrika, there is a lack of research on the BMI distribution of its indigenous population, which has prompted the need for this study.

Study population: Three hundred and seventy-five (375) subjects were used for this research. The subjects were recruited from Okrika Island. The Slovin's formula (Antoro, 2024) was used to calculate the minimum sample size of subject in this research.

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)}$$

Where: n=Sample size, N=Population size (6000), and e=Significant level (0.05)

$n = \frac{N}{(1+Ne^2)}$ gives:

$$n = \frac{6000}{(1 + 6000 \times 0.0025)} = n = \frac{6000}{(16)} = 375$$

Materials used: The materials used for the measurement of the body mass index were weight scale, meter rule, Pen and Calculator, and a recording paper for data collection.

Measurements: To calculate the BMI, the measurements of weight (kg) and height (m^2) of the subjects was required. The height of the subject was measured using the meter rule. The subject stands erect in front of the meters rule, and the reading is marked and recorded. The weight of the subject was measured in a weight scale, and the reading recorded. Subsequently, the BMI was calculated using this standard BMI calculation formula (Murguía-Romero *et al.*, 2012)

BMI = weight (kg)/height 2 (m^2).

Foot Length was measured using steel measuring tape as the distance from the tip of the hallux (the great toe), while hand-Length of the subjects was measured from the mid-point below the radial and ulna tuberosity to tip of middle finger. All linear measurements were in centimeters for each parameter, but were converted to meter squared (m^2) when calculating for BMI.

The accuracy of the measurements was ensured via precautions that included removal of subjects' shoes before height measurement, erect standing on a level platform beside the meter rule while measuring heights, proper calibration of the weight scale prior to weight measurement, and prompt recording of accurate readings during height, weight and length measurements.

Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria: Only indigenous Okrika people of Rivers State whose parents, grandparent and great grandparents were are Okrika by origin were recruited for this study, while non-indigenes or pregnant indigenes encountered in the course of the study were excluded.

Ethical Consideration: Informed consent was duly requested from the subjects prior to their recruitment, and clarifications were made regarding the data being collected, which is strictly for the purpose of research and advancement of knowledge and human well-being.

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using the Z-test to determine the sex differences and $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant. A correlation analysis was also carried out between the height of subjects and their hand and foot lengths, as well as a regression analysis to predict the stature (height) of the males and females from their hand and foot lengths.

RESULTS

The result of the mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum and range of the measured parameters for both males and females are shown in the tables below (Table 1), indicating that the mean values for the weight of males and females were 71.36 ± 12.24 and 65.52 ± 13.96 respectively, which is significantly higher in males than in females ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Mean values of measured parameters for both males and females.

Variable	Sex	Total count	Mean SD	Minimum	Maximum
Weight(kg)	M	179	71.36 ± 12.24	44.00	105.00
	F	196	65.52 ± 13.96	40.00	102.00
Hand Length (cm)	M	179	18.83 ± 2.04	13.21	24.13
	F	196	17.48 ± 2.03	13.21	21.59
Foot Length(cm)	M	179	25.26 ± 2.70	17.02	35.56
	F	196	23.88 ± 2.34	17.02	29.21
BMI (kg/m^2)	M	179	23.11 ± 4.53	16.33	43.56
	F	196	23.34 ± 5.24	13.52	50.00
Height(cm)	M	179	176.38 ± 12.46	134.00	199.00
	F	196	168.03 ± 12.25	130.00	198.00
Height(m)	M	179	1.76 ± 0.12	1.34	1.99
	F	196	1.68 ± 0.12	1.30	1.98

The mean values of hand length were 18.83 ± 2.04 in males and 17.48 ± 2.03 in females. The mean value was also observed to be significantly higher in males than in females ($p < 0.05$). The mean values for Foot Length was 25.26 ± 2.70 in males and 23.88 ± 2.34 in females. The males showed a significantly higher mean value for the above measured parameter than the females ($p < 0.05$). The mean values for Body Mass Index in both males and females were 23.11 ± 4.53 and 23.34 ± 5.24 respectively. There was no significant difference observed between the mean value for the

males and that of the females ($p > 0.05$). The mean value for Height (cm) was 176.38 ± 12.46 in males and 168.03 ± 12.25 in females. The mean value was observed to be significantly higher in males than in females ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2 shows the linear regression equation for estimating height from hand length for the male subjects. The result can be used for predicting the height of the male Okrika people from their hand length and foot length.

Table 2: Regression Equation for Height from Hand and Foot length for male subjects.

Variable	Regression Equation
Hand Length(cm)	Height = $108 + 3.63 \text{ Hand Length(cm)}$
Foot Length(cm)	Height (cm) = $109 + 2.65 \text{ Foot Length(cm)}$

Figure 1 and 2 below shows the Pearson Correlation for Body Mass Index and Weight (Kg) for males and females respectively. It was observed that there was a positive correlation between the measured parameters.

Figure 1: Showing Pearson Correlation for Body Mass Index and Weight for males (Kg) $r = 0.639$.

Similarly, figure 3 and 4 below shows the Pearson Correlation for Height (cm) and Hand Length (cm) for males and females respectively. It was observed that there was a positive correlation between the measured parameters.

Figure 2: Pearson Correlation for Body Mass Index and Weight for females (Kg) $r = 0.734$.

Figure 3: Pearson Correlation for Height (cm) and Hand Length (cm) for males $r = 0.596$.

Figure 4: Pearson Correlation for Height (cm) and Foot Length (cm) for females $r = 0.604$.

DISCUSSION

Knowledge of BMI is crucial in assessing ethnic differences, sexual dimorphism, and fat distribution. Kayla, 2009 concluded that males were more likely to under-assess their weight than females, but this study found the opposite, with females under-assessing their weight more frequently than males. Additionally, more females were in the overweight category than males, contradicting Eckel (2003), who reported that men are more likely to be overweight. Schvey *et al.* (2013) suggested that weight and gender influence juror perception of guilt, but this study found no correlation, as many obese individuals encountered were friendly. This suggests that obese individuals should not be discriminated against, as fat distribution can be influenced by lifestyle. Findings from this study align with Oladipo *et al.* (2011), who reported an increase in BMI with age due to body composition changes. The cultural impact on body size perception, as observed by Metcalf *et al.* 2000; Lofton *et al.*, 2023), is consistent with this study, particularly among Okrika women who participate in the *Iria* (fattening room) tradition.

Education level was also found to influence BMI perception, aligning with Metcalf *et al.* (2000), who found that individuals with lower education levels tend to have a higher BMI and lower awareness of body size (Khalaf *et al.*, 2021). This study also supports Sahasporin *et al.* (2002), who reported that overweight black women correctly perceived their weight and maintained positive self-image, in contrast to white women who were more dissatisfied. Similarly, Bhuiyan *et al.* (2003) found that black individuals tend to perceive their weight as lighter than white individuals, which is in line with the present study. Physical activity plays a critical role in weight control, as noted by Ravussin *et al.* (1989), but many Okrika people lead sedentary lifestyles due to employment in the oil industry.

When comparing BMI across different populations, (Bell *et al.* 1998; Liu *et al.*, 2021) found that white populations had a higher BMI than the Okrika people. Studies on Mexican Americans (Bell *et al.*, 1998) and Caucasians also indicated higher weights compared to this study. However, while Japanese males had a higher mean weight than Okrika males,

Okrika females had a higher weight than Japanese females. Latinos, on the other hand, exhibited higher weight values than those in this study. Furthermore, Bell *et al.* (1998) found that Chinese individuals had a lower BMI than the Okrika people, and Filipino females had a lower BMI than Okrika females. The present study's BMI values were also higher than those of the Ikwerre ethnic group (Oladipo *et al.*, 2010) but lower than the Mexican American and Asian American BMI values (Bell *et al.*, 1998; Liu *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, Igbos had a higher BMI than the Okrika people (Oladipo *et al.*, 2011), and Caucasian males had a higher BMI than Okrika males (Maskarinec *et al.*, 2009). The Yoruba people, as reported by Olayiwola and Ketiku (2006), had a lower BMI than the Okrika people, while Japanese females had a higher BMI than Okrika females.

Foot length comparisons indicate that Igbo and Hausa males had longer foot lengths than the Okrika males (Fawehinmi and Paul, 2008), while Okrika males had longer foot lengths than Japanese males. These variations emphasize the need for ethnic-specific anthropometric data.

Thus, the findings of this study provide baseline data on the BMI, hand length, and foot length of the Okrika ethnic group. The findings will be valuable to biomedical technologists, clinicians, and forensic anthropologists in understanding body composition within this ethnic group. The data should be utilized in clinical assessments specific to the Okrika ethnic group, and further research should be conducted on BMI variations among other ethnic groups in Nigeria.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors acknowledge the efforts of all research assistants involved in this study. Their contributions in participant recruitment and anatomical measurements are deeply appreciated

REFERENCE

- Amini, P. and Isaac, C. (1998): Establishing a chronology for Ekpeye History; Emhai Print. and Pub, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, OCLC 53842667; 5-6.
- Antoro, B. (2024). Analisis penerapan formula slovin dalam penelitian ilmiah: kelebihan, kelemahan, dan kesalahan dalam perspektif statistik. *Jurnal Multidisiplin Sosial Dan Humaniora*; 1(2): 53-63
- Asuk, O. C. and Adubo, I. (2020). Andoni (Obolo) and Okrika diasporas in historical perspectives. *Icheke Journal of the Faculty of Humanities*; 18(2): 507-528.
- Bhuiyan, A.R., Gustat, J., Srinivasan, S.R. and Berenson, G.S. (2003). Differences in body shape representations among young adults from a biracial (Black-White), semirural community: the Bogalusa Heart Study. *Am J Epidemiol*; 158(8):792-7. doi: 10.1093/aje/kwg218. PMID: 14561669.
- Bosy-Westphal, A. and Müller, M. J. (2021). Diagnosis of obesity based on body composition-associated health risks—Time for a change in paradigm. *Obesity Reviews*; 22: e13190.
- Bouchard, C. (2021). Genetics of obesity: what we have learned over decades of research. *Obesity*, 29(5), 802-820.
- Bouchard, C., Tremblay, A., Després, J. P. *et al.* (1990). The response to long-term overfeeding in identical twins. *The New England Journal of Medicine*; 322(21): 1477–1482.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM199005243222101>

Clark J. David (1971): "Ekpeye: A Language of Nigeria" Ethnologue reading and writing Ekpeye Institute Of African Studies, University Of Ibadan, Nigeria, Oclc 2464074.

Bell A. Colin, Linda S. Adair and Barry M. Popkin, (2002) Ethnic differences in the association between BMI and Hypertention. Johns Hopkins Bloomerg School of Public Health, *American Journal of Epidemiology*; 155: 346-353

Diaz E.O, Prentice A.M and Goldberg G.R (1992): Obesity Management, *Am J Clin Nutr*; 641; 55-56

Eckel R.H (2003). Obesity; disease or physiologic adaptation. In; Eckel RH, Ed. Obesity; Mechanisms and Clinical Management. Baltimore; Tenth edition Lippincott Williams and Wilkins. P 35.

Fawehinmi H.B and Aladipo G.S (2004): "Foetal Origins" Of Late-Onset Disease: A focus on Cardiovascular and Metabolic Diseases. First edition, University of Port Harcourt Press Monograph: P. 3-13.

Fardon Richard and Furniss Graham (2009): African languages, development and the state. Routledge. ISBN 0-415-09476-3: 66

Gilberts, E.C., Arnold, M.J., and Grobbee, D.E. (1994) Hypertension and Determinants Of Blood Pressure With Special Reference To Socioeconomic Status In A Rural South Indian Community. *J. Epidemiol. Community Health*; 48: 258 – 61.

Hall, K. D., Farooqi, I. S., Friedman, J. M., Klein, S., Loos, R. J., Mangelsdorf, D. J., ... and Tobias, D. K. (2022). The energy balance model of obesity: beyond calories in, calories out. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*; 115(5): 1243-1254.

Hill J. O and Donahoo W.T (2003). Environmental influences on obesity. In; Eckel Rh, Tenth Ed. Obesity; Mechanisms and Clinical management, Williams and Wilkins, pp. 75-90.

Huayi, Z., Gang, X., Laiyuan, L. and Hui, H. (2023). Age-and sex-related trends in body composition among Beijing adults aged 20–60 years: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*; 23(1): 1519.

Jones G.I. (2000): The trading states of the oil rivers: a study of political development in eastern Nigeria. Lit Verlag Berlin-Hamburg-Münster,

Jebb S.A., Prentice, A.M. and Goldberg, G.R (1996): Obesity management, *Am J Clin Nutr*; 259: 64-66.

Khalaf, A., Al Hashmi, I. and Al Omari, O. (2021). The Relationship between Body Appreciation and Self-Esteem and Associated Factors among Omani University Students: An Online Cross-Sectional Survey. *Journal of Obesity*; 2021(1): 5523184.

King, N. (1830): His life and times riverside communications, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. 978-31226:5- 6

Lichtman, S. W., Pisarska, K., Berman, E. R., Pestone, M., Dowling, H., Offenbacher, E. *et al.* (1992). Discrepancy between self-reported and actual caloric intake and exercise in obese subjects. *The New England Journal of Medicine*; 327(27): 1893–1898. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM199212313272701>

Liu, B., Du, Y., Wu, Y., Snetselaar, L. G., Wallace, R. B. and Bao, W. (2021). Trends in obesity and adiposity measures by race or ethnicity among adults in the United States 2011-18: population based study. *BMJ*; 372.

Lofton, H., Ard, J. D., Hunt, R. R. and Knight, M. G. (2023). Obesity among African American people in the United States: a review. *Obesity*; 31(2): 306-315.

Lorraine Reitzel (2013). Cancer Prevention and Risk Assessment through the Center for Community-Engaged Translational Research; American Journal of Public Health: The University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center.

Levine, J. A., Eberhardt, N. L. and Jensen, M. D. (1999). Role of nonexercise activity thermogenesis in resistance to fat gain in humans. *Science*, 283(5399), 212–214. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.283.5399.212>.

Maskarinec, G., Grandinetti, A., Matsuura, G., Sharma, S., Mau, M., Henderson, B.E., and Kolonel, L.N. (2009). Diabetes prevalence and body mass index differ by ethnicity: the Multiethnic Cohort. *Ethn Dis.*; 19(1):49-55. PMID: 19341163; PMCID: PMC2702477.

Maurice, E.S., Moshe Shike, C.R.A., Benjamin, C. and Robert J.C. (1999): Modern Nutrition in Health and Disease. Baltimore; Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, Tenth edition. P 1018.

Metcalf, P.A., Scragg, R.K.R., Willoughby, P., Finau, S. and Tipene-Leach, D. (2000): Ethnic differences in perceptions of body size in middle-aged European, Maori and Pacific People living in New Zealand, *International Journal of Obesity*;24(5): 593-599

Mohajan, D. and Mohajan, H.K. (2023). Body mass index (BMI) is a popular anthropometric tool to measure obesity among adults. *Journal of Innovations in Medical Research*; 2(4), 25-33.

Murguía-Romero, M., Jiménez-Flores, R., Méndez-Cruz, A. R., and Villalobos-Molina, R. (2012, October). Improving the body mass index (BMI) formula with heuristic search. In *2012 11th Mexican International Conference on Artificial Intelligence*; pp. 100-104. IEEE.

Oladipo, G.S, Akande, P.A., Anugweje, K.C. and Osogba, I.G. (2011): Waist Circumference and Waist-to hip ratio in Adult Igbo of Nigerian Interrelation with risk of Cardiovascular Disease. *Current research Journal of Biological Sciences*; 3: 82-87.

Oladipo, G.S., Okoh, P.D., Ugboma, A.H. and Yorkum, K.L. (2010): Study of BMI and Waist to Hip Ratio of Ogoni and Ikwerre adult in Nigeria. *British Journal of Dairy Sciences*; 1(1): 6-9.

Olayiwola I.O. and Ketotu, A.O. (2006): Socio-demographic and Nutritional Assessment of the elderly Yorubas in Nigeria. *Asia Pac J Clin Nutr*; 15: 95-101.

Picton, J. (1988) "Ekpeye masks and masking" *African arts*; 94: 46–53,

Ravussin, E. and Burnand, .B (1989): Nutrition and Health Disease. *American Medical Journal of Clinical Nutrition*; 573: 256

Reyes, M.U., Mesenburg, M.A. and Victora, C. G. (2020). Socioeconomic inequalities in the prevalence of underweight, overweight, and obesity among women aged 20–49 in low-and middle-income countries. *International Journal of Obesity*; 44(3): 609-616.

Maskarinec G, Grandinetti A, Matsuura G, Sharma S, Mau M, Henderson BE, Kolonel LN. Diabetes prevalence and body mass index differ by ethnicity: the Multiethnic Cohort. *Ethn Dis.* 2009 Winter;19 (1):49-55. PMID: 19341163; PMCID: PMC2702477.

Paeratakul, S., White, M.A., Williamson, D.A., Ryan, D.H. and Bray, G.A. (2002). Sex, race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and BMI in relation to self-perception of overweight. *Obes Res*; 10(5):345-50. doi: 10.1038/oby.2002.48. PMID: 12006633.

Santalla, Kayla Jade, (2009). Race and Obesity: An exploratory analysis of perceptions and experiences related to weight among black and white adults" *Open Access Theses*. P. 45.

Sarma, S., Sockalingam, S. and Dash, S. (2021). Obesity as a multisystem disease: Trends in obesity rates and obesity-related complications. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*; 23: 3-16.

Segal, K. R., Lacayanga, I., Dunaif, A., Gutin, B. and Pi-Sunyer, F. X. (1989). Impact of body fat mass and percent fat on metabolic rate and thermogenesis in men. *American Journal of Physiology*; 256(5 Pt 1): E573–E579.

Stewart, W. K., & Fleming, L. W. (1973). Disorders of metabolism. Postgraduate Medical Journal: Management. Baltimore; Lippincott. P. 203–209.

Škop, V., Guo, J., Liu, N., Xiao, C., Hall, K. D., Gavrilova, O., & Reitman, M. L. (2023). The metabolic cost of physical activity in mice using a physiology-based model of energy expenditure. *Molecular metabolism*, 71, 101699.

Skov AR, Toubro S, and Buemann et al (1997). *Clin Physiol*; 17: 279.

Schvey N. A, Puhl R.M, Levandoski K.A and Brownell K.D (2013): Defendant Weight and Perceptions Of Guilt: *International Journal of Obesity, Macmillan Publishers Limited*: 1–7.

Watson, L. B., Lewis, J. A. and Moody, A. T. (2019). A sociocultural examination of body image among Black women. *Body Image*; 31: 280-287.

Whitney, E.N. and Rolfes, S.R. (2002), Understanding Nutrition. Toronto. Ontario: Wadsworth group. P. 63-75.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

Okoseimiema, S.C. conceived and designed this study. Kalio, E., Ebhojaye, I.K., Sunday, I.P., Christian, U., Obomanu-Tamunotonjo, R. and Collins, G.U. collaborated with Okoseimiema, S.C. in executing the study, including data collection, analysis, as well as the manuscript drafting and revisions.

